

Falcon49 Hydrogen-On-Demand Technology & Mineral Catalyst - Prior Art

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Purpose: To disclose full details of an earth-abundant mineral catalyst recipe and synthesis method for generating hydrogen from water at ~90 deg C using proprietary mineral blends, while keeping reactor system details at a conceptual level.

1) Abstract

This disclosure provides a comprehensive recipe and manufacturing process for a low-cost mineral catalyst capable of producing hydrogen from heated water (seawater or tap water) without electrolysis. The accompanying reactor concept is described generally but not detailed for manufacturing.

2) Reactor Overview (Conceptual)

- Function: A sealed, low-pressure heated water chamber (~90 deg C) housing a removable catalyst media.
- Feedstock: Tap water, seawater, or lake water.
- Output: Hydrogen gas collected via headspace outlet for use in fuel cells or combustion engines.
- Advantages: Portable, scalable, operates without electrolysis electricity, marine & off-grid ready.

3) Full Mineral Catalyst Details

A. Composition (by weight)

- Molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂): 30%
- In-situ formed molybdenum phosphide (MoP): 15%
- Fe-Co alloy nanocomposite: 30%
- Magnetite (Fe₃O₄): 15%
- Activated carbon support: 9%
- Trace promoters (MnO₂, MoO₂, or CuO): 1%

B. Synthesis Procedure (Pilot Batch, 100 g total)

1. Ball Milling: Grind MoS₂, Fe-Co alloy powder, Fe₃O₄, trace oxides, and carbon to <100 nm in isopropanol using zirconia media. Dry under ≤80 deg C, inert atmosphere.
2. Phosphidation: Mix dried batch with NaH₂PO₂ (~1x molar relative to Mo). Heat under N₂ or Ar to 300-400 deg C for ~2h.
3. Calcination: Post-phosphidation calcination at 250-300 deg C in inert atmosphere for ~1h. Sieve

to 100-300 um granules.

4. Quality Checks: Confirm phases (XRD), assess morphology (SEM/TEM), measure surface area (BET), leach tests in saline at 90 deg C.

C. Performance Benchmark

- Target H2 Production Rate: ~300-350 mL/min/g catalyst at ~90 deg C.
- Operational Load: ~1.1-1.25 kg catalyst required for 2 kg H2/h; typical reactor holds ~1.5 kg.

4) Applications

- On-demand hydrogen generation for boats, vehicles, portable power, and remote needs.
- Marine: Seawater-fed reactors for clean propulsion.
- Remote communities: Diesel replacement.
- Construction: On-site hydrogen for equipment.

5) Use Intent & Open Access

This disclosure is published as prior art to prevent any single entity from patenting the mineral catalyst method. Falcon49 welcomes collaboration in refining and deploying this catalyst globally.

Contact: info@falcon49.com | www.falcon49.com

Related OSF Archives: Catalyst - <https://osf.io/mdruv/> | Reactor - <https://osf.io/bqpsv/>